

SUPERPLASTICITY OF CERAMIC PARTICULATE REINFORCED MAGNESIUM ALLOY COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY A MELT STIRRING METHOD

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SUMMARY: The superplasticity at high strain rate was investigated for the TiC_p/Mg-5wt.%Zn and the AlN_p/Mg-5%Al composites, fabricated by a melt stirring method, extrusion and hot rolling. For the TiC_p/Mg-5wt.%Zn composites with $V_f = 0.20$, a strain rate sensitivity of 0.3 and the total elongation of 300 % were exhibited in a strain rate of $6.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ at 743K. The m value of the AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composites was 0.4 and the maximum total elongation was about 200% in strain rate of 0.5s^{-1} at 673~698K. The fracture surfaces of these composites showed fibrous features, indicating the presence of a kind of glass phase, which was resulted from tensile testing temperature below the solidus temperature of the composites. The presence of a glass phase can apparently enhance the HSRS phenomenon in Mg matrix composites.

KEYWORDS: magnesium matrix composite, high strain rate superplasticity, melt-stirring method, titanium carbide, aluminum nitride

INTRODUCTION

A magnesium matrix composites has a great potential to apply to automobile, aerospace industries since the density of magnesium is low as compared with other metal alloys and the composite is expected to achieve excellent mechanical, physical and thermal properties [1~3]. High Strain Rate Superplasticity (HSRS) is expected to offer the efficiently near-net shape forming method for aluminum matrix composites, since HSRS materials usually exhibit an elongation of 250~600% at a high strain rate of about $0.1 \sim 10 \text{s}^{-1}$ [4~12]. However, superplastic magnesium alloys and magnesium matrix composites developed up to date were Mg-8.5wt.%Li-1wt.%Y, ZK60 and AZ61 which indicate the total elongation of 460~700 % at a lower strain rate of $3 \sim 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$ and at a temperature of 453~623K because of their relatively larger grain size of about $35 \mu\text{m}$ [13~17] and Mg-9wt.%Li-5wt.%B₄C with a fine-grain of $2 \mu\text{m}$ prepared by a foil metallurgy can produce superplastic behavior at 423~473K [14]. These Mg alloys and the composite are conventional superplastic materials.

It was found that a SiC_p/ZK60 composite made by PM methods shows an m value of 0.5 and the total elongation of 350% at very high strain rate of about 1.0s^{-1} [16] and that a TiC_p/Mg-5wt.%Zn composite fabricated by a melt stirring method can produce an m value of about 0.3

and the total elongation of 300% at the strain rate of $0.1s^{-1}$ [17]. The results show that it is important to investigate systematically an effect of component of composites such as size and volume fraction of reinforcement, matrix alloys and interfaces between reinforcement and matrix on superplastic characteristics of magnesium matrix composites.

The purpose of this study is to reveal the HSRS in ceramic particulate reinforced Mg alloy composite fabricated by a melt stirring method. In addition, the superplastic deformation mechanism of the Mg matrix composite will be discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

TiC (average particle size of 2-5 μ m) and AlN (that of 0.72 μ m) particles were used as reinforcement. Molten magnesium alloy heated at 973K was stirred with pre-heated TiC and AlN particles in a magnesia crucible under argon atmosphere by using a melt stirring method. The volume fraction (V_f) of TiC particle was 0.10 and 0.20. In the case of $V_f=0.10$, the stirring was performed for about 350 seconds and in the case of $V_f=0.20$, the stirring time was about 450 seconds. The stirring time was about 420 seconds and the V_f was 0.15 for AlN particle. The as-cast composite was further solidified in permanent mould. Table 1 and 2 show chemical composition of magnesium alloy matrix and ceramic particles.

Table 1 Chemical compositions of magnesium, aluminum and zinc (wt.%)

	Mg	Al	Cu	Mn	Pb	Zn	Fe	Si
Mg	99.96	0.003	0.001	0.006	----	----	0.006	0.003
Al	----	99.99	0.001	----	----	----	0.002	----
Zn	----	tr.	----	----	0.002	99.99	tr.	----

Table 2 Chemical compositions of AlN and TiC particles

	Fe	Si	Cu	Mn	Mg	Zn	Ni	Cr	O	N	Na	TiC
AlN	ppm 22	ppm 26	ppm 7	ppm 3	ppm 2	ppm 2	ppm 2	ppm 2	wt.% 0.99	wt.% 33.4		
TiC	wt.% 0.1							wt.% 0.03		wt.% 0.008		wt.% 99.46

Hot extrusion and hot rolling were used to produce the HSRS composite. The hot extrusion was performed at an extrusion ratio of 44 at a temperature of 673K. Subsequent hot rolling was carried out at 698K. Thickness reduction per each pass was less than 0.1 and the reheating time between each rolling pass was about 5 minutes. The final thickness of the hot-rolled composite was less than 0.75mm. Tensile specimens with a 4mm gage width and a 5.5mm gage length were made. Specimens were deformed at 673, 698, 723 and 743K in strain

rates ranging from 1×10^{-4} to 2 s^{-1} . Microstructure and fracture surface of the samples were examined by SEM and TEM.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 1 show the SEM microstructures of TiC_p/Mg alloy composites fabricated by (a) melt stirring, (b) melt stirring and extruding and (c) melt stirring and extruding, further hot-rolling (denoted by hot-rolled, hereafter), respectively. Although reinforcement-free magnesium layer and TiC particulate agglomerate are present in as-cast composite(a) and in the even as-extruded(b), TiC particles were noted to be dispersed homogeneously in the hot-rolled composite(c) and defects were removed.

HSRS of TiC_p/Mg -5wt.%Zn composite

The flow stress, σ , relates to true strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}$, via the equation $\sigma = k \dot{\epsilon}^m$. In the equation, the strain rate sensitivity exponent, m , is the slope of the curve $(\text{dln } \sigma / \text{dln } \dot{\epsilon})$, where k is a constant incorporating structure and temperature dependencies. Normally, the m value must be larger than 0.3 in order to observe superplasticity in a material. A high m value material can suppress the development of necking and leads to a high total elongation.

Fig.1 SEM microstructures of TiC_p/Mg -5wt.%Zn composite fabricated by (a) melt stirring, (b) melt stirring and extruding and (c) hot-rolling and extruding after melt stirring.

Fig. 2 . Relationships (a) between the flow stress and the strain rate and (b) between the total elongation and the strain rate of $TiC_p/Mg-5wt.\%Zn$ composite melt stirred, extruded and hot-rolled.

The relationship between the flow stress and the strain rate of the hot-rolled $TiC_p/Mg-5wt.\%Zn$ composites with volume fractions of $V_f=0.10$ and 0.20 is shown in Fig.2(a). The flow stress of the both composites increases linearly with increasing strain rate. The strain rate sensitivity value of the composite with $V_f=0.20$, m , is about 0.43 at $743K$ and in strain rate range from 0.067 up to $0.33s^{-1}$, but the m value of the composite with $V_f=0.10$ is about 0.33 in strain rate range from 0.017 up to $0.167s^{-1}$. This result is in agreement with the HSRS observations in ceramic whisker or particulate reinforced aluminum alloy composites [4~7].

Total elongation of the $TiC_p/Mg-5wt.\%Zn$ composite as a function of strain rate is shown in Fig.2(b). A maximum total elongation of about 300% was obtained at the strain rates of $0.067s^{-1}$. At strain rates greater than $0.17s^{-1}$, the elongation value begin to decrease, despite the fact that the m value remains high (see Fig. 2(a)). It is attributed to excessive cavitation in test samples deformed under extremely-high strain rate.

Generally, a total elongation of over 100% can be obtained in a wide strain rate region from $0.01s^{-1}$ up to $0.7s^{-1}$. The results suggest that casting defects in the $TiC_p/Mg-5wt.\%Zn$ composite fabricated by melt stirring method can be removed by extrusion and hot rolling. In particular, these thermomechanical processes are very effectively in dispersing TiC particle and to produce homogeneous microstructure. The reason that the maximum elongation value does not coincide with the maximum m value.

Superplastic Characteristics of Mg-5wt.%Al Alloy

The relationship between the flow stress and the strain rate of the hot-rolled Mg-5wt.%Al alloy is shown in Fig.3(a) as a function of temperature. The logarithmic flow stress of the Mg-5wt.%Al alloy increases approximately with increasing logarithmic strain rate and decreasing temperature. The strain rate sensitivity value of the Mg-5wt.%Al alloy is about 0.25 at 673~723K in strain rates range from 2.0×10^{-4} to 0.6 s^{-1} . And the Mg-5wt.%Al alloy does not have threshold stress in strain rate range from 2.0×10^{-4} to 1.5 s^{-1} .

Fig.3 Superplastic characteristics of Mg-5wt.%Al alloy fabricated by a melt stirring method before extruding and hot-rolling.

Total elongation of the Mg-5wt.%Al alloy is shown in Fig.3(b) as a function of temperature. The total elongation at 673K and 698K becomes less than 150% in the strain rate range from 2.0×10^{-3} to $2.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, but the elongation at 723K increases more than 150% in the strain rate range from 2×10^{-4} to $2 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Maximum total elongation of about 300% in the Mg-5wt.%Al alloy is obtained in the strain rate of $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 723K. Therefore, the results indicate that the Mg-5wt.%Al alloy alone is a conventional superplastic alloy.

HSRS of AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al Composite

The relationship between the flow stress and the strain rate of AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composite hot-rolled after extrusion is shown in Fig.4(a). The flow stress of the composite increases with increasing strain rate and decreasing temperature. The m value of the composite becomes less than 0.1 in strain rate range less than 0.1 s^{-1} , which means that the composite has a threshold stress in the relatively lower strain rate range. However, the m value of the composite increases to 0.39~0.43 in the strain rate from about 0.1 s^{-1} to 1.5 s^{-1} at 673~698K. These high m values reveal that the AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composite can produce the HSRS in the higher strain rate

range, but the m value of the composite deformed at 723K decreases to 0.18 in the same strain rate range.

Fig. 4 Superplastic characteristics of the AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composite fabricated by a melt stirring method before extruding and hot-rolling.

The maximum total elongation of more than 200% is obtained in the composite in a high strain rate of about 0.5s^{-1} at 673~698K as shown in Fig.4(b). By comparison, the composite deformed at 723K shows the maximum total elongation of about 200% at a higher strain rate of 1.2s^{-1} . At relatively lower strain rates less than 0.1s^{-1} , the total elongation begins to decrease in temperature range of 673~723K, which is coincident with the fact that the m value is very low. The decrease of elongation in the relatively lower strain rate range might be attributed to excessive cavitation during high strain rate deformation[13]. Nonetheless, a total elongation of over 100% can generally be obtained in a wide strain rate range (0.02s^{-1} to 1.2s^{-1}). The results suggest that hot rolling after extrusion can effectively produce homogeneous microstructure in the AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composite and leads to HSRS, and it is noted that the optimum strain rate of about $0.5\sim 1.0\text{s}^{-1}$ for the AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composite is higher by 10 times than that in the TiC_p/Mg-5wt.%Zn composite and it is thought that the result is caused by fine AlN particle size of $0.72\mu\text{m}$.

Microstructure

The TEM microstructures of the AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composite hot-rolled is shown in Fig.5. The grain size of the composite before test and after superplastic deformation is less than about $2\mu\text{m}$ and fine AlN particle is dispersed homogeneously along grain boundaries so as to retain grain growth during hot rolling, heating and superplastic deformation. Therefore, it is

thought that primary deformation mechanism of the HSRS for the AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composite is grain boundary sliding.

Fig.6 shows relationship between total elongation and strain rate for the TiC_p/Mg-5wt.%Zn with TiC volume fraction of 0.10, 0.20[17] and the AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composites and the Mg-5wt.%Al matrix made by a melt stirring method and for the SiC_p/ZK60 PM composite[16]. Arrows with the numbers of (1)~(5) in Fig.6 indicates optimum strain rate of the superplastic materials at which maximum total elongation is obtained. The TiC_p/Mg-5wt.%Zn composite with $V_f=0.20$ has the grain size of about 2 μm [17] and matrix of the SiC_p/ZK60 PM composite consists of grains with 0.5 μm [16] and the AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composite includes the grain size of less than 2 μm but the grain size of the Mg-5wt.%Al alone becomes more than 20 μm . The optimum strain rate in Fig.6 is arranged in order of SiC_p/ZK60 > AlN_p/Mg-5%Al > TiC_p/Mg-5%Zn ($V_f=0.20$) > TiC_p/Mg-5%Zn ($V_f=0.10$) > Mg-5%Al alone. Therefore, the results reveal that optimum strain rate at which maximum total elongation is obtained in magnesium matrix composites is associated with grain size.

Fig.5 TEM microstructures of AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composite hot-rolled.

CONCLUSIONS

The superplastic characteristics of Mg-5wt.%Al matrix, TiC_p/Mg-5wt.%Zn and AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composites, fabricated by a melt stirring method, extrusion and hot-rolling were investigated. The following results were obtained

- (1) Mg-5wt.%Al alloy indicates a m value of about 0.25 and the total elongation of about 300% was obtained in low strain rate of 10^{-3}s^{-1} at 723K.
- (2) The composite had a threshold stress in strain rate range lower than 0.1s^{-1} , although the flow stress of Mg-5wt.%Al alloy decreased simply with decreasing strain rate.
- (3) The strain rate sensitivity (m value) of the AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al composites is about 0.40 in strain rate range higher than 0.1s^{-1} and the composite hot-rolled after extrusion exhibited a total elongation of about 200% in strain rate of 0.5s^{-1} at 673~698K.
- (4) The m value of the TiC_p/Mg-5wt.%Zn composites with $V_f=0.20$ is about 0.33 and the total elongation of about 300% was obtained in strain rate of 0.067s^{-1} at 743K.

- (5) The composites have a fine grain size of about $2\mu\text{m}$ since TiC and AlN particles were dispersed homogeneously along grain boundaries so as to avoid grain growth during superplastic deformation.
- (6) The fracture surface of the composites showed fibrous features and a presence of glass phase which is resulted from excessive sliding in TiC particle-Mg and AlN particle-Mg matrix alloy interfaces.

Fig. 6 Relationships between the total elongation and the strain rate of TiC_p/Mg-5wt.%Zn((1), (2)), AlN_p/Mg-5wt.%Al(3), PM SiC_p/ZK60(4) composites and Mg-5wt.%Al matrix(5).

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